

imum (352) cropped days/year (see table). Rice – rice – rice used 283 days, and rice plus 2 vegetable crops (rice – knolkhol – lady’s finger) used 240 days.

Three rice crops produced maximum grain yield (11 t/ha) followed by rice –

maize – cowpea, with 8.3 t grain/ha. Rice – rice – rice yielded significantly more dry matter, followed by jute – rice – groundnut. Rice – knolkhol – lady’s finger yielded the least dry matter.

Results indicate that three sequential

rice crops give highest grain yield, and that rice – maize – cowpea can be grown to obtain reasonable grain yields with more efficient soil and water management. □

Water table depths and dynamics aid interpretation of drought-prone rainfed lowland rice variety trials

J. C. O’Toole, D. P. Garrity, and M. A. Maguling, IRRI

During the 1980 to 1982 wet seasons, we assessed the effects of water table depth in 11 environments in the Philippines on grain yield of elite and advanced breeding materials of the Rainfed Lowland Yield Trial for Drought-Prone Areas.

Polyvinylchloride tubes placed in the field to a depth of 20 cm and 60 or 100 cm were observation wells for measuring the water table depth. Average water table depth (AWD) during the yield-determining reproductive and grain-filling stages was calculated by summing the daily values from panicle initiation to 10 d before harvest. Plants are most sensitive to water stress at these stages. Water table depth was summed individually for each maturity class: very early (<105 d), early (105-115 d), medium (115-130 d), and late (>130 d).

Figure 1 shows the relationship of average water table depth and grain yield for each maturity group. Each point is an average of the two highest yielding varieties or lines for each location. By using the highest yielding entries we hoped to negate the effects of other biological and physical-chemical factors that determine growth and yield, and thus focus on the role of subsurface water in rainfed wet-land culture.

There was a significant correlation for all but the medium-maturity entries in the shallow water table.

In the deeper water table, correlation was significant for all but the early maturing group. Grain yield generally decreased as water table depth decreased regardless of maturity group.

At some sites where water table depth during the crop season was very low, we obtained high grain yield. This might have

1. Relationship between grain yield of the 2 highest yielding entries at each location and average water table depth in the root zone above the hardpan (0 to 20 cm) and below the paddy (0 to 60 or 100 cm) soil surface. The average water table depths were summed from 30 d before flowering to 20 days after flowering based on mean flowering date of each maturity group.

2. Water level in paddy (piezometer at 20 cm) and below the paddy (piezometer at 60 cm), and rainfall at Oton, Iloilo, Philippines, 1981 wet season.

been caused by adequate amount and distribution of rainfall, and not total rainfall. For example, at Iloilo in 1981 wet season (Fig. 2), rainfall was well distributed from 10 d before flowering to 20 d after flowering, with a total rainfall of

154 mm for the early-maturing group and a mean grain yield of 3.9 t/ha.

At Guimba in 1980 wet season, rainfall was high (347 mm) during the same growth stages but mean grain yield was low, 2.1 t/ha, because of a short-term

water deficit after flowering in mid-Oct (Fig. 3).

Our results suggest that recording of water table depths within and below the rice field can be a useful indicator of field level hydrology. When used in tandem with meteorological data, especially rainfall, these easily measured parameters allow interpretation of crop water stress at remote sites. They are not only currently practical methods for use in large variety trials where conventional soil or plant water status measurement techniques are impossible. The daily nature of these hydrological values allows interpretation of yield response to water stress for each growth stage of the rice crop.

Although numerous other biological, physical, and chemical factors contribute to site-specific stresses that determine yield, recording field hydrological conditions aids significantly in interpreting differences in nursery performance over years and locations. □

3. Water level in paddy (piezometer at 20 cm) and below the paddy (piezometer at 100 cm), and rainfall in Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, 1980 wet season.

The International Rice Research Institute

P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines

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